
WORK ETHICS AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHERS' JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study examined work ethics as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions guided the study and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study is 6,598 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. The sample of 660 teachers (that is, 10% of teachers' population) was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. Two instruments were used for data collection: Work Ethics Questionnaire (WEQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ). The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts while construct validation was carried out with Principal Component Analysis approach. The reliability of the instruments was trial tested in Enugu State using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient and the average coefficient values of 0.785 for WEQ and 0.851 for TJCQ are considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Simple linear regression analysis was used for the study. The study revealed that discipline ($r = 0.542$ $p = 0.000$), teamwork ($r = 0.563$ $p = 0.000$), work attitude ($r = 0.551$ $p = 0.000$) positively and significantly predicted teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study concluded that good practices of work ethics is helpful for teachers to do their work satisfactorily and committedly for the achievement of most desired quality secondary education in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that school administrators should from time to time organize sensitization programmes for teachers on work ethics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Keywords: Work Ethnics, Job commitment, Discipline, Teamwork, Work attitude

Introduction

Teachers who equipped themselves with the right values and work behaviour consider the importance of the school's strategic direction to support the implementation of the school's vision and mission. Thus, the work ethics of teachers are given priority because they can affect not only the commitment of teachers but also the effectiveness of teachers in the school. Hence, schools need to establish policies and practices that guide the teachers' work behaviour. Failing to inculcate the right work values in the secondary school teachers can greatly affect their job commitment in schools.

Teachers' job commitment in secondary schools is the strength of a teacher's identification and involvement with the teaching job. It determines whether a person will leave or remain in the teaching profession or not. Kaegon and Okere (2023) defined teachers' job commitment as a psychological state that characterizes a teacher's relationship with his or her profession, and has implications for the decision to remain involved with it. It is the emotional bond between the teacher and the school. Teachers' job commitment is regarded as a power or quality needed to approach stress and change. It includes factors such as honesty, responsibility, and tolerance for fallibility. Teachers' job commitment is of importance as it is associated with greater job effort and involvement, that is, committed employees are less likely to leave their position and display other withdrawal behaviour such as absenteeism. The strength of any profession depends upon the degree of commitment of its members. Thus, teachers' job commitment is the strength of teachers' identification with and involvement in the school organization. It can be viewed as the dedication that teachers believe or perceive towards particular work and the job they carry out in the school. Obiekwe *et al.* (2024) described job commitment as total organism direction involving not only the conscious mind but the whole direction which is gradually achieved by the individual through a close relationship in which even unconscious tendencies are as much respected as conscious choices. Obiekwe *et al.* further noted that commitment in job is a state of attachment that defines the relationship between an actor (an individual, a group or organization) and an entity (commitment target). They disclosed that the determinants of organizational commitment include; strong desire to stay in the organization, acceptance of the organization's values, and willingness to work hard to achieve organizational goals.

Teachers' job commitment is their engagement in statutory obligations in the school. Onafowope *et al.* (2023) defined teachers' job commitment as the willingness of teaching staff to put their efforts and time in performing their duties. Teachers' job commitment is the state of being loyal and devoted in executing instructional responsibilities in the school. Odoh and Nwite (2022) defined teachers' job commitment as their dedication, attachment and involvement in their work or duties in order to accomplish task and achieve positive outcomes or good results. Teachers' job commitment is the dedication of teaching staff towards their duties. Contextually, teachers' job commitment is the work attitude and behaviour exhibited by teaching staff towards attainment of predetermined educational goals and objectives. In this study, teachers' job commitment was measured with the following indices. Teachers who are committed to their job are punctual to work, deliver instruction at the stipulated period, cover scheme of work and participate in school functions. Eziuzo *et al.* (2024) opined that a teacher who is committed and loyal to his or her job exhibits positive behaviours at school such as punctuality, dedication to school work, making extra time for students after school hours, implementing diverse teaching methods in the classroom and improvising instructional materials when they are not available. Committed teachers comply with professional code of conduct and maintain high level of discipline.

Work ethics is work attitudes or traits into the workings of a person or a group of the nation. The work ethics is manifested by the simple living and hard work. The work ethic is often much echoed by the leader to his men to be in performing their duties. Work ethics refer to cultural norm that places a positive moral value on doing a good job due to the belief that work has intrinsic value for its own sake. Nwogbo and Ugwuoke (2022) defined work ethics to be accepted standards in terms of personal and social welfare of employee, their work attitudes, self-discipline and commitment to their assignments. Obianuju and Ikediugwu (2023) also defined work ethics as a manner of conduct binding on an individual or a group in the work place, which makes them conform to the ethical standards as a result of which organizational output level and the resultant profitability level are influenced positively.

Work ethics help to regulate the activities of employees in different situations in the organisation. The habit of following good work ethics is intrinsic, that is, the work ethics an individual displays come from his or her values. The values of an individual according to Nwogbo and Ugwuoke (2022) are dependent on the environment, experiences and life-long influences. These influences include the parents, teachers, friends, peers, competitors anyone or anything that has helped to shape or form the person's opinion of the world. Similarly, Edo and Bulopakaye (2024) described work ethics to be part of the responsibilities of the organization and thus, expected employees' commitments enclosed in the core values and principles of the organization. This suggested that work ethics can be widely seen as the guideline an organization and its executives can use to generate sound decisions. This is so because the work ethics comprises of the set standards articulated in law and regulations, internal policy, and procedures. For instance, being honest, working with integrity, respect, and fairness are based on the principles, which are expected from employees and customers in terms of service delivery, product quality, health, safety, and efficiency. Various measures of work ethics have been used in assessing compliance to certain behaviours and set ethical requirements. Arjay and Joelyn (2022) mentioned organizational justices, discipline, appreciation and praise, teamwork and work attitude as work ethics in organizations. Similarly, Nwogbo and Ugwuoke (2022) included sense of integrity, responsibility, honesty, dedication, justices, discipline, work attitude and sincerity as work ethics.

The researchers defined work ethics as to teachers' commitment to the fulfillment of their responsibilities with the sense of integrity, honesty, dedication and sincerity in schools. Specifically, the researcher is of the view that work ethics is about what is morally correct, honourable and acceptable to the larger majority of teachers working in schools. Although different organizations including schools set different tools of work ethics in achieving their desired vision, the most critical of these measures are reflected in the perspective of organizational discipline, teamwork and work attitude which is the trust of the study.

Discipline is the state of orderliness and obedience to the guiding principles or laid down rules of an organization. Ehiane (2024) defined discipline as a conscious effort geared towards training and developing peoples' character to follow an instituted order or an ethical standard of conduct in an organization. The existence of well-disciplined teachers and students as exhibited by conforming to laid down rules, respect of oneself, self-control, orderliness, and displaying acceptable patterns of the behaviour is one of the indicators of principals' managerial effectiveness. Ibezim and Ikediugwu (2023) stated that well-disciplined teachers comply with school rules, regulations and policies which improve their job commitment. A disciplined teacher is also one who complies with the rules and regulations in school's pursuit of predetermined goals which could be done through teamwork.

Teamwork is the ability to work together towards a common vision. It is a well-known fact that teamwork is not only the foundation of all successful managements, but the means of improving overall results in organizational productivity. It is that variable that allows common people to attain uncommon results. Teamwork facilitates employees to cooperate with each other, improve their skills and deliver useful responses without any dispute between them (Kaegon & Okere, 2023). The essence of teamwork is to encourage division of labour, specialization and ultimately increased productivity. The importance of teamwork in terms of productivity sees employees coming together to achieve same goals and objective for the good of the organization. Umar and Sha'awa (2023) opined that teamwork refers to a group of human beings that have high performance with its members along with the spirit that enables them to achieve the group's goals in the workplace with confidence and cooperation and reduces the workload for everyone, which enables them to exchange ideas. Teamwork is the ability to actively participate in the pursuit of the specific objectives of the organization where performance and a positive attitude are required. Teachers' attitude to work is very important and plays a significant role in helping students choose and seek their interest, set goals for themselves, propel them in the right and proper directions of lives.

Work attitude plays an important role in manipulating the work performances of teachers in schools. The way teachers behave in the school often relies on how they feel about their job which implies that understanding the work attitude of teachers is determined by their behaviour in the schools. Invariably, this ignites the necessity to recognise, measure, and boost teachers' attitudes towards work. Arjay and Joelyn (2022) defined work attitude as a conviction or predisposition to behave in a certain way at the workplace as a result of an individual experience as well as personality. Organizations, like individuals, can be characterised and observed as rigid, welcoming, earnest, inventive, traditional or otherwise. Such qualities, as well, can serve as aspects to envisage attitudes and behaviours of the people within these organizations. Uwannah *et al.* (2023) viewed work attitude as a set of behaviour and judgments to work, and such behaviours and thoughts are redirected in form of work involvement and organizational commitment. It is the actions and inactions of employees toward their work that determines commitment and productivity.

Teachers' work attitude is affective feelings of like and dislike that causes teachers to have a positive or negative behaviour towards their job. The attitude of teachers towards their work considerably influences their behaviour towards it. It may be positive (favourable) or negative (unfavourable); if the work attitude of teachers is negative, then they will not be able to succeed in their profession. Students draw from their teachers' work attitude to form their own attitude which may eventually affect their learning outcome (Obianuju & Ikediugwu, 2023). Thus, work attitude of teachers is a strong work ethics.

Furthermore, there is a growing concern in society that some principals have been found wanting in their task of administration of the school and its resources, including the teachers. Perhaps, this is due to inadequate work ethics traits which could jeopardize the commitment of teachers to the educational system. Some of these inadequacies in the area of work ethics traits include indiscipline, negative work attitude, lack of teamwork between the principal and the staff, lack of the absence of commitment on the part of the teachers has been seen as an explanation for a variety of ills, among which is absenteeism, negative work attitude, irregularities in the classroom and indiscipline among teachers. The above does not give room for collaboration between the principals and the teachers, and the adverse effect of this is on the students. As such, how work ethics predict job commitment of teachers in

public secondary schools in Anambra State is still in doubt and requires very urgent research attention, hence the need for this present study.

Statement of the Problem

The scenarios of some teachers sneaking out of school during official hours to attend to their personal affairs, presenting ill-prepared lessons, exhibiting of poor role models to students, absenting from school and classes makes one wonders if they are committed to their job in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The unethical and uncommitted attitude of teachers towards their job may be attributed to the existence of conflict, indiscipline, poor record management, low rapport, and ill-motivation of teachers in public secondary schools in the state. The incessant cases of failure of teachers to effectively execute tasks assigned to them could be traceable to poor delegation of duties approaches of public secondary school principals in Anambra State. Teachers' adherence to professional ethics and work attitude in public secondary schools are shaped by their irrespective rules and regulations. Public secondary schools have varied rules and procedures for taking disciplinary action which could account for dissimilarity in the punctuality, absenteeism and habitual lateness to work among teachers in public secondary schools. Despite all the rules and regulations in public secondary schools, there are still traces of poor job commitment among teachers; could this be traceable to work ethics trait in the school? It is against this backdrop that this study was conceived by the researchers to examine work ethics as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine work ethics as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine how:

1. Discipline predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Teamwork predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Work attitude predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does discipline predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of teamwork on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. How does work attitude predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Discipline does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Teamwork does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Work attitude does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods:

The study adopted a correlational research design. The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria. The population of 6,598 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six education zones in Anambra State was used for the study. The sample of 660 teachers was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. Two researcher's structured instruments were used for data collection: Work Ethics Questionnaire (WEQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ). The instruments are structured in three sections namely A, B and C. Section A deals with the personal data of the respondents, while sections B and C deals with WEQ and TJCQ.

Work Ethics Questionnaire (WEQ) which was structured by the researchers measured work ethics of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instrument WEQ contained 30-items spread across three Clusters 'A-C.' Cluster 'A' elicited information on discipline with 10-items; Cluster 'B' elicited information on teamwork with 10-items; and Cluster 'C' elicited information on work attitude with 10-items. These items were placed on 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) (4 points), Agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (SD) (1 point).

Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJSQ) as structured by the researchers measured job commitment of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instrument TJCQ has 20-items with a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) (4 points), Agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (SD) (1 point).

The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation, all in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus Nigeria. On the other hand, construct validation was carried out with the help SPSS v.25. Construct validity of the instruments for work ethics, school cultural norms and teachers' job commitment components loading seven factors was explored using Principal Component Analysis approach. The instruments were trial-tested in a single administration on a representative sample of 30 teachers randomly selected from five public secondary schools in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State. Enugu State was chosen for the test because both states have similar educational system. The responses of the respondents were collated to determine the internal consistency of the item in each cluster. This was done using Cronbach Alpha. The instruments were administered to the respondents by the researchers with the help of six research assistants. Simple linear regression analysis was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

For Regression Coefficient (r)

- + Sign = Positive Prediction
- Sign = Negative Prediction

The negative sign means a negative coefficient which indicates a negative prediction or correlation between variables, while a positive sign means a positive coefficient which indicates a positive prediction or correlation between variables.

For Sig. (2-tailed) when

- Sig. (2-tailed) < .05: Reject H_0 and Accept H_1
- Sig. (2-tailed) > .05: Do not reject H_0

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of 0.05 the null hypotheses was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: How does discipline predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis with discipline as it predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	B
Constant	27.457	6.235	
Discipline	.583	.391	.542
R	.542		
R ²	.437		
Adj. R ²	.401		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that discipline positively predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.542$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.437 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 44% of the variations in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in school discipline. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.401 indicating that 40% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (school discipline). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of discipline is moderately strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Nevertheless, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.542$) showed that school discipline is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit improvement in teachers' discipline led to 0.542(54%) improvement in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of school discipline on teachers' job commitment means that teachers' job commitment moderately depends on the proper and adequate application of teachers' discipline in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the predictive value of teamwork on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis with teamwork as it predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	B
Constant	30.221	5.217	
Teamwork	.598	.284	.563
R	.563		
R ²	.485		
Adj. R ²	.457		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 2 indicated that teamwork positively predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.563$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.485 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 49% of the variations in teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in school teamwork. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.457 indicating that 46% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers’ job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (school teamwork). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of teamwork is moderately strong in determining the teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. More so, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.563$) showed that school teamwork is a positive predictor of teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit rise in school teamwork led to 0.563 (56%) rise in teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of school teamwork on teachers’ job commitment means that teachers’ job commitment moderately depends on the prompt improvement of school teamwork in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 3: How does work attitude predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Summary of simple regression analysis with work attitude as it predicts teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	B
Constant	29.348	5.874	
Work Attitude	.586	.295	.551
R	.551		
R^2	.489		
Adj. R^2	.446		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 indicated that work attitude positively predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.551$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.489 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 49% of the variations in teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers’ work attitude. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.446 indicating that 45% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers’ job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers’ work attitude). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of work attitude is moderately strong in determining the teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. More so, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.551$) showed that teachers’ work attitude is a positive predictor of teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit development in teachers’ work attitude led to 0.551(55%) upsurge in teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers’ work attitude on teachers’ job commitment means that teachers’ job commitment moderately depends on the good practices of teachers’ work attitude in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₁: Discipline does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with discipline does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	27.457	6.235		23.296	.000
Discipline	.583	.391	.542	19.452	.000
R	.542				
R ²	.437				
Adj. R ²	.401				
F	34.642				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.542 while the R² is 0.437 and Adjust R² is 0.401. The F-ratio associated with regression is 34.642, the t-test is 19.452 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that discipline does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that discipline significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₂: Teamwork does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with teamwork does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	30.221	5.217		25.531	.000
Teamwork	.598	.284	.563	22.416	.000
R	.563				
R ²	.485				
Adj. R ²	.457				
F	36.214				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 5 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.563 while the R² is 0.485 and Adjust R² is 0.457. The F-ratio associated with regression is 36.214, the t-test is 22.416 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that teamwork does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that teamwork significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₃: Work attitude does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with work attitude does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized	t-	p-
	β	β	β	value	value
Constant	29.348	5.874		24.131	.000
Work Attitude	.586	.295	.551	21.368	.000
R	.551				
R ²	.489				
Adj. R ²	.467				
F	35.325				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 9 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.551 while the R² is 0.489 and Adjust R² is 0.467. The F-ratio associated with regression is 35.325, the t-test is 21.368 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that work attitude does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that work attitude significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of the Findings

Findings on how discipline predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that discipline positively and significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding showed that principals establish rules to guide the professional conduct of teachers, issue query to erring staff to dampen further misconduct, discourage misconduct among staff through oral caution, use threats to control unacceptable behaviour among teachers and instruct misbehaved staff to sign letter of undertaken to discourage the repetition of a particular misconduct. This finding lend credence to the findings of Ehiane (2024) that school principals exhibited effectiveness on discipline to ensure teachers behave in a desirable way in the workplace. Edo and Bulopakaye (2024) submitted that principals' effectiveness on discipline helps to ensure that teachers adhere to rules, regulations and procedures that are deemed necessary for enhancing their job commitment in schools. Without any iota of doubt, discipline in any school is as a result of self-control, obedience to the rule of law, restraining oneself, forbearance and trustworthiness from teachers (Ibezim & Ikediugwu, 2023).

A disciplined teacher is a teacher who is characterised with integrity, commitment, transparency, accountability, perseverance and prudence. A teacher that is disciplined is a teacher that is willing to deny self per time to achieve the institutional goal. It is the affirmation of self-control or self-will above mere cravings. This is synonymous to self-discipline. Sibomana and Andala (2024) asserted that, a teacher that practices self-discipline has the capacity to resist behavioural temptations, be it in the private or public with a determination of pressing forward to exhibiting what is right. It is therefore safe to conclude that defilement of disciplinary expectations of any school teachers will greatly affect teaching and learning of such school. This will consequently undermine the efforts of the school in realizing its goals.

Findings on how teamwork predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State showed that teamwork positively and significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The finding of the

study is not surprising because principals in many schools under review set up teams that could assist them in delivering on their mandate of effective administrative practice. This result is in consonance with Umar and Sha'awa (2023) that the presence of teamwork amongst staff in the school brings about high performance of the school to coordinate works into work groups so as to tap from the respective human resources the school possesses. The findings of Quines and Nino (2023) indicated that the presence of properly instituted teams or committees in the school to facilitate school activities will not only bring about good students' performance but also a productive administrative system in the school. A team exists when individual strengths and skills are combined with teamwork in the pursuit of a common cause in order to produce meaningful results for the team members and the organisation (Edo & Bulopakaye, 2024).

The study in collaboration with Obionu *et al.* (2024) exhibited a positive and significant relationship which could be as a result of friendly, collaborative, strong bonds of loyalty and tradition in the schools as they have similar features which promote teachers' job commitment in schools. More so, Edo and Bulopakaye (2024) asserted that when teams are built, team members share the goals and objectives of the school organisation, which helps the school organisation, achieve better outcomes. Thus, team building also helps to improve teachers' job commitment at work, which contributes to increased teachers' job productivity. Umar and Sha'awa (2023) pointed out that when the right team is built, it helps to reduce absenteeism and work defects and also increases productivity. This does not only benefit the school organisation but also improves the efficiency and effectiveness of the various employees in the team.

Findings on how work attitude predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State showed that work attitude positively and significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding may have resulted because having the right attitude towards work and work processes improves teachers' job commitment and performance in schools. This finding is in line with the study of Obianuju and Ikediugwu (2023) that teachers having a positive attitude towards work have a positive and significant influence on students' academic performance which is indicative of teachers' job commitment and performance in schools. Nwogbo and Ugwuoke (2022) noted that teachers who display positive attitude towards work are always motivated to perform and eager to put in their best in achieving schools' goals and objectives. Furthermore, Arjay and Joelyyn (2022) reported that there is close relationship between teachers' professional attitude and their performance. Arjay and Joelyyn further revealed that professional teachers' attitude performs better in the teaching and learning process. The findings of Uwanna *et al.* (2023) showed that teachers who have positive attitude towards work are motivated towards their profession. They are punctual in the school. They respect their students and their colleagues in schools.

Conclusion

The study has shown that work ethics is pervasive and powerful. For schools, they are forces for positive change or definite barriers for the desired change. For teachers, it is either the glue that bonds them to the school or what drives them away. The study concluded that good practices of work ethics is helpful for teachers to do their work satisfactorily and committedly for the achievement of most desired quality secondary education in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

1. School administrators should from time to time organize sensitization programmes for teachers on work ethics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. School principals should help their teachers in understanding that discipline management is key for success and therefore set aside budget for trainings as well as facilitations for good work ethics practices in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Principals should make an effort to come up with measures that can boost teachers' contribution towards teamwork, and show gratitude to those who exhibit exemplary behaviours and sacrifices for the success of teams in the school. This practice will spur and motivate staff to perform optimally in their jobs.

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